

Efficiency of source and method of Zn application for IR6.^a Tamboli (Sheikhupura), Pakistan.

Zn application method	Zn deficiency symptoms ^b 25 DT	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers/plant (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Efficiency of Zn application
Control (no Zn)	7	113.3 a	11.1 bc	5.63 c	—
Soaking the seed in 1% ZnSO ₄ solution for 24 h before seeding (0.25 kg ZnSO ₄ /ha)	4	113.6 a	12.5 ab	6.20 ab	2300.0
Dipping the sprouted seed in 1% ZnO suspension (0.25 kg ZnO/ha)	3	114.5 a	12.4 ab	6.28 ab	2628.0
Broadcasting ZnSO ₄ at 10 kg/ha on nursery bed before seeding (0.25 kg ZnSO ₄ /ha)	5	113.6 a	11.6 abc	5.89 abc	1056.0
Broadcasting Zn frit before transplanting at last puddling (0.25 kg/ha)	5	113.2 a	10.9 bc	5.81 bc	748.0
Broadcasting Zn frit mixture before transplanting at last puddling (0.25 kg/ha)	7	113.4 a	10.5 c	5.52 c	—
Dipping the nursery roots in 1% ZnO suspension	1	116.4 a	13.1 a	6.75 a	1119.0
Dipping the nursery roots in 1% ZnSO ₄ solution	1	116.4 a	13.1 a	6.74 a	1117.0
Broadcasting ZnSO ₄ at 10 DT (10 kg/ha)	2	115.0 a	12.7 ab	6.34 a	73.2

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other (DMRT). DT = days after transplanting. ^bSymptoms were recorded visually in a scale of 0-10: 0 = no deficiency, 10 = severe deficiency.

where nursery roots were dipped in ZnO suspension and ZnSO₄ (see table). Treatments affected productive tillers and yield significantly, but not plant height.

Dipping sprouted seed and nursery

roots in 1% ZnO suspension before seeding or transplanting was the most efficient method of curing Zn deficiency, followed by dipping sprouted seed and nursery roots in 1% ZnSO₄ solution and broadcasting 10

kg ZnSO₄/ha on the nursery bed before seeding. Broadcasting 10 kg ZnSO₄/ha 10 d after transplanting was least efficient. □

Biofertilizers for rice and their residual effect on rabi crops in Madhya Pradesh, India

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A field experiment was conducted to measure the response of rice to applications of fresh biofertilizers blue-green algae (BGA), *Azospirillum*, and *Azotobacter* and their residual effect on rabi crops. Soil was clay loam with 180-16-450 kg available N, P, and K/ha. Plot size was 8 m × 5 m in kharif, divided into 4 subplots of 5 m × 2 m for rabi crops.

Rice was transplanted on 16 Jul and harvested on 19 Oct 1984. Rabi crops were sown on 20 Nov and harvested 14 Mar–10 May 1985. Rice received 18 kg P and 10 kg K/ha. The table shows the treatments.

BGA was applied in 5-7 cm standing water 7 d after transplanting; growth

was sufficient to fix atmospheric N. Seedling roots were soaked 6 h in a solution of *Azospirillum* and *Azotobacter* before transplanting.

Rice yield was significantly higher with 10 kg BGA and the 2 N levels than in the control, but not with 15 and 20 kg BGA, showing erratic

response to inoculation (see table). Only chickpea responded significantly to residual fertility of biofertilizers.

However, all the treatment yields were significantly greater than that of the control. Residual effects of biofertilizers can be obtained in succeeding crops such as chickpea. □

Effect of BGA, *Azospirillum*, *Azotobacter*, and N on rice yield and residual effects on rabi crop yields. Madhya Pradesh, India, 1984-85.

Treatment	Yield ^a (t/ha)				
	1984 kharif rice (Ratna)	1984-85 rabi			
		Wheat (Lok-1)	Chickpea (JG62-404)	Linseed (R552)	Mustard (Varuna)
Control (no fertilizer)	3.2	1.0	1.5	0.3	1.0
10 kg BGA/ha	3.9	1.1	2.1	0.3	1.2
15 kg BGA/ha	3.2	1.0	1.9	0.4	1.0
20 kg BGA/ha	3.6	1.0	1.8	0.3	0.9
40 kg N/ha	4.1	1.0	1.9	0.3	1.0
60 kg N/ha	4.1	1.1	1.9	0.3	1.0
<i>Azospirillum</i>	3.5	0.9	1.9	0.4	1.0
<i>Azotobacter</i>	3.4	0.9	2.1	0.3	1.0
CD (0.05%)	0.5	ns	0.4	ns	ns

^aVarieties used are in parentheses.